

1 **Calling behaviour under climate change: geographic and seasonal variation of**
2 **calling temperatures in ectotherms**

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5 *Running head:* Calling temperatures in ectotherms

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 Calling behaviour is strongly temperature-dependent and critical for sexual selection
29 and reproduction in a variety of ectothermic taxa, including anuran amphibians, which
30 are the most globally threatened vertebrates. However, few studies have explored how
31 species respond to distinct thermal environments at time of displaying calling
32 behaviour, and thus it is still unknown whether ongoing climate change might
33 compromise the performance of calling activity in ectotherms. Here, we used new
34 *audio-trapping* techniques (automated sound recording and detection systems) between
35 2006 and 2009 to examine annual calling temperatures of five temperate anurans and
36 their patterns of geographic and seasonal variation at the thermal extremes of species
37 ranges, providing insights into the thermal breadths of calling activity of species, and
38 the mechanisms that enable ectotherms to adjust to changing thermal environments. All
39 species showed wide thermal breadths during calling behaviour (above 15 °C) and
40 increases of calling temperatures in extremely warm populations and seasons. Thereby,
41 calling temperatures differed both geographically and seasonally, both in terrestrial and
42 aquatic species, and were 8–22 °C below the specific upper critical thermal limits
43 (CT_{max}) and strongly associated with the potential temperatures of each thermal
44 environment (operative temperatures during the potential period of breeding). This
45 suggests that calling behaviour in ectotherms may take place at population-specific
46 thermal ranges, diverging when species are subjected to distinct thermal environments,
47 and might imply plasticity of thermal adjustment mechanisms (seasonal and
48 developmental acclimation) that supply species with means of coping with climate
49 change. Furthermore, the thermal thresholds of calling at the onset of the breeding
50 season were dissimilar between conspecific populations, suggesting that other factors
51 besides temperature are needed to trigger the onset of reproduction. Our findings imply

52 that global warming would not directly jeopardise calling behaviour in study species,
53 although might affect other temperature-dependent features of their acoustic
54 communication system.

55

56 **Introduction**

57 Climate warming forces species to confront changing thermal environments, and may
58 jeopardise the performance of the basic physiological functions of organisms, especially
59 in ectotherms (Pörtner & Knust, 2007; Deutsch *et al.*, 2008; Kearney *et al.*, 2009; Huey
60 *et al.*, 2009; Duarte *et al.*, 2011). As a consequence, ongoing climate change has already
61 caused shifts in their geographic distribution (Parmesan *et al.*, 1999; Parmesan & Yohe,
62 2003; Wilson *et al.*, 2005; Hickling *et al.*, 2005; Pöyry *et al.*, 2008), reproductive
63 phenology (Beebee, 1995; Roy & Sparks, 2000; Gibbs & Breisch, 2001; Parmesan &
64 Yohe, 2003; Hassall *et al.*, 2007; Bartomeus *et al.*, 2011) or ecological interactions
65 (Harrington *et al.*, 1999; McCarty, 2001; Bale *et al.*, 2002; Walther *et al.*, 2002; Visser
66 & Both, 2005; Parmesan, 2006), and it even may be involved in regional and major
67 extinctions (Pounds *et al.*, 2006; Sinervo *et al.*, 2010). Predictions of the compensatory
68 response of ectotherms to climate change, which is an urgent and challenging task in
69 current biology, depend upon comprehending the ecological performance of key
70 biological functions under different thermal environments (Pörtner & Knust, 2007;
71 Buckley, 2008; Kearney *et al.*, 2009; Huey *et al.*, 2009), and the mechanisms that
72 underlie the thermal adjustments of the species (Helmuth *et al.*, 2005; Angilletta, 2009).

73 Calling behaviour plays a prominent role in sexual selection and reproduction in a
74 wide variety of ectothermic taxa, including anurans, fish, and insects (e.g., Bradbury &
75 Vehrencamp, 1998; Fay & Popper, 1999; Gerhardt & Huber, 2002), which comprise the
76 large majority of terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity (Wilson, 1992; Groombridge,
77 1992). Acoustic displays are used to attract mates, defend resources, ward off
78 opponents, and respond to predation risks, and hence are crucial for individual fitness.
79 However, sound production in ectotherms is strongly influenced by temperature (Bellis,
80 1957; Walker, 1957, 1962; Lörcher, 1969; Schneider, 1974; Gerhardt & Mudry, 1980;

81 Gayou, 1984; Pires & Hoy 1992; Márquez & Bosch, 1995), as well as other features of
82 an acoustic communication system. Thus, environmental temperatures beyond specific
83 thermal thresholds may constrain physiological processes associated with sound
84 production to such an extent as to inhibit calling behaviour (Lörcher, 1969; Schneider,
85 1974; Walker 1975; Gayou, 1984; Gerhardt & Huber, 2002). As a result, temperature
86 considerably affects seasonal and diel calling patterns by modifying the onset, timing,
87 and the intensity of the calling episodes and consequent reproductive activity (Blair,
88 1961; Heinzmann, 1970; Schneider, 1971; Blankenhorn, 1972; Salvador & Carrascal,
89 1990; Fukuyama & Kusano, 1992; Henzi *et al.*, 1995; Navas, 1996a; Brooke *et al.*,
90 2000; Oseen & Wassersug, 2002; Murphy, 2003; Steelman & Dorcas, 2010; Llusia *et*
91 *al.*, 2013a).

92 Although calling behaviour is a key, widespread, and temperature-dependent life-
93 history trait among ectotherms, few studies have explored how species respond to
94 distinct thermal environments at time of displaying calling behaviour (e.g., Navas,
95 1996a), and thus it is still unknown whether ongoing climate change might compromise
96 the performance of calling activity in ectothermic taxa. Prior to adaptation, ectotherms
97 depend on complex thermal adjustment mechanisms to persist in new environments
98 (e.g., Feder & Burggren, 1992; Angilletta, 2009). Thermal breadth determines the range
99 of temperatures that permit some level of performance of organisms (Huey &
100 Stevenson, 1979; Lutterschmidt & Hutchison, 1997; Angilletta, 2009), and hence
101 constrains their response capacity to new thermal environments (Deutsch *et al.*, 2008;
102 Huey *et al.*, 2009; Kearney *et al.*, 2009; Sinervo *et al.*, 2010; Duarte *et al.*, 2011). Yet
103 plasticity mechanisms (e.g., seasonal or development acclimation) lead to shifts in
104 thermal sensitivity and preferred body temperatures (Rome *et al.*, 1984; Angilletta *et*
105 *al.*, 2006; Calosi *et al.*, 2008; Gvoždík, 2012) that may provide species with means to

106 cope with climate warming. In ectotherms communicating by acoustic signals, calling
107 temperatures are important components of specific thermal performance breadth
108 because of the critical and temperature-dependent function of calling behaviour.
109 Examining calling temperatures and their patterns of geographic and seasonal variation
110 in different thermal environments (e.g., thermal extremes of species range) provides
111 insights into the thermal breadth of calling activity of species, and the physiological and
112 behavioural mechanisms that enable ectotherms to adjust to heterogeneous and
113 changing thermal environments.

114 Here we test for the first time whether ectotherms exhibit fixed or divergent calling
115 temperatures when they are exposed to distinct thermal environments. Previous studies
116 have found clear differences in calling and reproductive phenology of ectotherms across
117 spatial (i.e., latitude and altitude gradients) and temporal scales (i.e., recent global
118 warming) that have been associated with changes in environmental temperatures
119 (Schneider, 1971; Beebee, 1985, 1995; Roy & Sparks, 2000; Gibbs & Breisch, 2001;
120 Parmesan & Yohe, 2003; García-París *et al.*, 2004; Hassall *et al.*, 2007; Bartomeus *et*
121 *al.*, 2011), and hence this suggests that calling behaviour takes place at specific thermal
122 ranges. According to these patterns, we predict that ectotherms will show fixed calling
123 temperatures when subjected to distinct thermal environments because of being
124 constrained by a narrow thermal breadth during calling behaviour. Therefore, species
125 would depend on acute thermoregulatory mechanisms to maintain reproductive activity
126 at stable thermal ranges across dissimilar or changing thermal environments (Huey,
127 1982; Rosen, 1991; Angilletta *et al.*, 2006). Alternatively, it could be expected that
128 ectotherms showing divergent calling temperatures among populations and seasons
129 reflect a wide thermal breadth during calling behaviour. The ability to perform at a
130 broad range of different temperatures might result from physiological adaptation (Hertz

131 *et al.*, 1983) or plasticity of thermoregulatory behaviour by seasonal or developmental
132 acclimation (Angilletta *et al.*, 2006; Calosi *et al.*, 2008; Gvoždík, 2012). Thus, the latter
133 hypothesis (*divergent* calling temperatures), as opposed the former one (*fixed* calling
134 temperatures), implies that the impacts of ongoing climate change on ectotherms might
135 be mitigated by the compensatory potential of their thermal adjustment mechanisms.

136 Anuran amphibians in a temperate habitat were used as a case study to address this
137 question. Amphibians are undergoing population declines in all biomes and at a higher
138 rate than other vertebrate groups (Stuart *et al.*, 2004; Wake & Vredenburg, 2008;
139 Hoffmann *et al.*, 2010), so that more than a third of all species are currently considered
140 as threatened. In addition to habitat loss or emergent diseases that have caused local
141 extinctions among amphibian species (Alford & Richards, 1999; Blaustein & Kiesecker,
142 2002; Bosch *et al.*, 2001; Becker *et al.*, 2007), global warming has also been identified
143 as a potential risk of population declines and extinctions in amphibians (Bernardo &
144 Spotila, 2006; Wake & Vredenburg, 2008; Dillon *et al.*, 2010; Duarte *et al.*, 2011).
145 Moreover, climate change is involved in synergies and interactions with other threats
146 (Pounds *et al.*, 2006; Bosch *et al.* 2007; Hof *et al.* 2011), exacerbating the deleterious
147 impacts on amphibian diversity.

148 In this study, we tested the hypothesis that ectotherms maintain fixed calling
149 temperatures when species are subjected to different thermal environments, as a result
150 of their restricted thermal breadth during calling behaviour, which might aggravate the
151 impacts of ongoing climate change on these taxa. Using new *audio-trapping* techniques
152 (i.e., automated sound recording and detection systems) between 2006 and 2009, we
153 measured annual calling temperatures of five temperate anurans (*Alytes obstetricans*, *A.*
154 *cisternasii*, *A. dickhilleni*, *Hyla molleri* and *H. meridionalis*) in populations located at
155 the thermal extremes (coldest vs. hottest) of their geographic distribution, and examined

156 whether calling temperatures were stable (i) between conspecific populations, (ii)
157 among breeding seasons, and (iii) close to the upper critical thermal limits (CT_{max}) of
158 study species. We also search for (iv) associations with three features of the thermal
159 environments (i.e., altitude, annual temperature, and potential temperature) that may
160 explain geographic patterns of calling temperatures. In addition, thermal thresholds of
161 calling at the onset of breeding season were also compared between conspecific
162 populations to explore (v) whether temperatures triggering calling behaviour are
163 concordant across species ranges. Finally, we discuss how our findings contribute to the
164 understanding and the predicting of the response capacity of ectotherms to new thermal
165 environments.

166 **Materials and methods**167 *Study species*

168 The reasons to select Iberian midwife toads (*Alytes obstetricans*, *A. cisternasii*, and *A.*
169 *dickhilleni*) and Iberian tree frogs (*Hyla molleri* and *H. meridionalis*) as study species
170 were threefold. First, acoustic communication in *Alytes* and *Hyla* is likely the most
171 extensively studied among the European anurans (Paillette, 1967; Schneider, 1974;
172 Crespo *et al.*, 1989; Márquez & Bosch, 1995, 1997; Bush, 1997; Dyson *et al.*, 1998;
173 Castellano *et al.*, 2002; Castellano & Rosso, 2007; Friedl & Klump, 2002, 2005; Friedl,
174 2006; Márquez *et al.*, 2006, 2011). Second, *Alytes* is one of the oldest clades within the
175 Palearctic anurans (Martínez-Solano *et al.*, 2004), whereas *Hyla* is a comparatively
176 recent clade (Stöck *et al.*, 2012). The large phylogenetic distance between these two
177 genera (Frost *et al.*, 2006) allows for comparisons of the thermal responses among
178 evolutionarily distinct anuran taxa. And third, they are suitable models of two
179 reproductive strategies among anurans, i.e. terrestrial vs. aquatic mating, which may
180 influence the selection and thermal dynamics of the calling habitats.

181 *Alytes* and *Hyla* males are vigorous callers that rely almost exclusively on acoustic
182 communication for the acquisition of females (Schneider, 1974; Márquez & Bosch,
183 1995). During the breeding season, males of both genera aggregate around water and
184 emit advertisement calls in noisy choruses. Otherwise, *Alytes* and *Hyla* exhibit clearly
185 distinct patterns of reproductive behaviour. *Alytes* are terrestrial anurans that typically
186 emit advertisement calls from underground refugia while buried or hidden, but
187 occasionally call from the ground surface (Márquez & Verrell, 1991; Márquez &
188 Bosch, 1995, 1996). The egg-laying of *Alytes* also occurs on land and subsequently
189 males carry the eggs away from the water for 4–5 weeks (Márquez, 1992). *Hyla molleri*

190 and *H. meridionalis* are aquatic egg-layers that vocalize mostly while floating on water,
191 but some males may also call from emergent vegetation or from the shore (Paillette,
192 1967; Schneider, 1974; Márquez & Tejedo, 1990; Márquez *et al.*, 2005).

193 All study species, except *A. cisternasii*, are prolonged, spring-to-summer breeders
194 that call during more than three months per reproductive season (Heinzmann, 1970;
195 Schneider, 1977; Márquez, 1992). *Alytes cisternasii* typically shows an explosive
196 breeding pattern (*sensu* Wells, 1977), which is strongly associated with the occurrence
197 of fall rains (López-Jurado *et al.*, 1979; Márquez, 1992). Three of these species are
198 restricted to the Iberian Peninsula, whereas *A. obstetricans* and *H. meridionalis* also
199 inhabit several areas of Western Europe or North Africa (Gasc *et al.*, 2004). Hence,
200 only two of the ten absolute thermal extremes of the range of the study species are
201 presumably outside of the Iberian Peninsula: the coldest one of *A. obstetricans* (Western
202 Europe) and the hottest one of *H. meridionalis* (North Africa).

203

204 *Study sites*

205 Calling temperatures were measured in ten populations of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1).
206 Two populations were selected per species, which were located at: (1) the cold thermal
207 extreme (hereafter, *CAo*, *CAC*, *CAd*, *CHmo*, and *CHme*), and (2) the hot thermal
208 extreme (hereafter, *HAo*, *HAc*, *HAd*, *HHmo*, and *HHme*) of the Iberian distribution of
209 the study species. *CAo*, *CAd*, and *CHmo* were in alpine grasslands above the timberline
210 in mountain sites of northern and southern Spain. Both study sites of *A. cisternasii* (*CAC*
211 and *HAc*) occurred in a temporary stream surrounded by open woodlands of live oaks
212 (*Quercus ilex* and *Q. suber*) in central and southern Spain. *CHme*, *HAd*, and *HHmo*
213 were in permanent ponds on agricultural lands of central and southern Iberia. *CHme* and
214 *HHmo* were sympatric populations. For the Iberian hot extreme of *H. meridionalis*

215 (*HHme*), acoustic monitoring was carried out in the coastal marshes (*Scirpus* spp.) of
216 the Doñana Biological Station in southern Spain. Recordings of calling activity of *A.*
217 *obstetricans* in its Iberian hot extreme (*HAo*) were conducted in an urban park in the
218 city of Coimbra, Portugal. Altitude and geographical coordinates of the study sites are
219 listed in Table 1.

220 To determine how extreme was the thermal regime of each study site, we compared
221 the annual mean temperature of the 10 x 10 km UTM square including the study site
222 (Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system; Hijmans *et al.*, 2005) with that of
223 the remaining 10 x 10 km UTM squares of the Iberian distribution of the study species
224 (Fig. 2; Pleguezuelos *et al.*, 2002; Loureiro *et al.*, 2008). In the Iberian Peninsula,
225 between 73% and 99% of the UTM squares of the species ranges had a higher annual
226 mean temperature than that of the UTM squares of the cold study sites. Conversely,
227 between 78% and 98% of the UTM squares had a lower annual mean temperature than
228 that of the UTM squares of the hot study sites (Table 1). Annual mean temperatures of
229 study sites ranged from 7.6 °C in the northernmost sites (*CAo* and *CHmo*) to 17.9 °C in
230 the southernmost one (*HHme*; Table 1). In addition to the temperature prerequisites
231 stated above, we selected populations that inhabited accessible locations in private or
232 restricted areas to facilitate servicing the equipment and to reduce potential sources of
233 human disturbance and damage to the equipment.

234 Field work was conducted between November 2006 and November 2009. All
235 populations were monitored for at least one entire breeding season (2007), except the
236 populations of *A. obstetricans* that were studied in 2009. Monitoring was extended 10–
237 12 weeks before and after the expected period of calling activity for each population to
238 ensure complete records. To examine seasonal variations on calling temperatures,
239 calling activity was recorded for two additional breeding seasons (2008 and 2009) in the

240 cold populations of *A. cisternasii* and *H. molleri*. Annual mean temperatures in the
241 Iberian Peninsula were similar between 2007 and 2008, and were up to 0.4 °C above the
242 average of annual mean temperatures in the 1971–2000 period. However, in 2009 that
243 average was exceeded by 1.2 °C, and hence 2009 was then, the third warmest year since
244 1965 in the Iberian Peninsula (AEMET, 2010). Thus, 2007–2009 comparison provides
245 an interesting framework to examine calling behaviour in extremely warm seasons.

246

247 *Equipment and sampling protocol*

248 To estimate annual calling temperatures for each population of the study species, calling
249 activity and operative temperatures were recorded with *audio-trapping* techniques based
250 on automated sound recording systems (ARS) and environmental data loggers. The
251 ARS were designed *ad hoc* and consisted of an omnidirectional condenser microphone
252 (FCM-626, Fonestar), a solid-state digital recorder (Marantz PMD660, D&M
253 Professional), and a custom-built programmable recording schedule controller (Western
254 Kentucky University; Cambron & Bowker, 2006). One ARS was deployed at each site,
255 housed in a watertight box, and placed to maximize the probability of detection of
256 anuran vocalizations. Microphones were placed 1–2 m above ground and protected
257 from rainfall and humidity by a plastic shield. The recording schedule was 3 minutes
258 per hour, 24 hours per day, during the whole study period. This sampling regime has
259 been shown adequate to detect calling activity of most temperate anurans, mainly
260 because the detection probabilities are rarely increased by longer or more frequent
261 recording periods (Shirose *et al.*, 1997; Dorcas *et al.*, 2010). To standardize the
262 recording sensitivity of each ARS, we followed the method described in Llusia *et al.*
263 (2011). Data download and battery replacement were carried out every three to four
264 weeks, and recording files (44.1 kHz, 16-bit, WAV or MP3-compressed) stored for

265 subsequent analysis. For the three-year monitoring, a second ARS (SM-1; Wildlife
266 Acoustics, Inc.) with the same settings was added to the recording stations at the *CAc*
267 and *CHmo* sites.

268 Operative temperatures was measured every 5 minutes with environmental data
269 loggers (HOBO Pendant 64 Kb and HOBO Pro v2, Onset Computer, Inc.) placed at the
270 *de facto* specific calling microhabitats of the study species (Navas, 1996a). For the
271 genus *Alytes*, operative temperature was measured in the shade at 5–10 cm deep of the
272 ground surface in the areas where terrestrial midwife toads called and mated (Márquez
273 & Verrell, 1991; Márquez & Bosch, 1995, 1996). For the genus *Hyla*, operative
274 temperature was measured in the water surface 1–2 m away from the shoreline in the
275 areas where aquatic tree frogs called and mated (Paillette, 1967; Schneider, 1974;
276 Márquez & Tejedo, 1990; Márquez *et al.*, 2005). HOBO Pendant data loggers were
277 selected as physical models because they have been found to reliably estimate operative
278 temperatures in small-sized ectotherms (Vitt & Sartorius, 1999; Navas & Araujo, 2000;
279 Dzialowski, 2005). The size of the data loggers was similar to those of both *Alytes* and
280 *Hyla* individual males, with dimensions (58 x 33 x 23 mm) within the range of body
281 size of the study species (García-París *et al.*, 2004). One HOBO Pendant data logger
282 was deployed at each study site during the whole study period. Air temperature (°C) and
283 relative humidity (%) were also measured for all study sites, with HOBO Pro v2 data
284 loggers placed 15–35 cm above ground in the vegetation that surrounded the breeding
285 areas, and with their logger probes protected from rainfall and direct sunlight. Accuracy
286 in the measurements was ± 0.3 °C for temperature and $\pm 2.8\%$ for relative humidity.

287 To determine the thermal variation within the calling microhabitats and to test for the
288 influence of data logger positions on temperature recording, simultaneous
289 measurements of operative temperature were taken at different locations during two

290 weeks of the breeding period at *CAo* (from May 15 to 30 2008), *CAC* (from November
291 15 to 30 2011), and *CHmo* (from July 23 to August 7 2008). HOBO Pendant data
292 loggers (n = 6 for *Alytes*; n = 4 for *Hyla*) were deployed in actual calling positions
293 within the microhabitat selected by each species in these study sites, following the
294 procedure described above. Air temperature was also recorded simultaneously at the
295 same dates with HOBO Pro v2 data loggers (n = 3–4).

296 Further, to determine the concordance of operative temperature recorded in the
297 calling microhabitats and actual body temperature of study species, we also measured
298 body temperature of calling males in populations of terrestrial species, i.e., *A. cisternasii*
299 (Valdemanco, Spain, 40°51' N, 3°38' W; 4–7 May 2013) and *A. dickhilleni* (Dílar,
300 Spain, 37°03' N, 3°33' W; 6–7 May 2013), and of aquatic species, i.e., *H. molleri*
301 (Valdemanco, Spain, 40°51' N, 3°39' W; 1–5 May 2013), and *H. meridionalis* (Santo
302 Aleixo, Portugal, 38°54' N, 7°25' W; 22–25 October 2003). Individuals were captured at
303 night-time during calling activity and their body temperature was determined
304 immediately by measuring cloacal temperature to the nearest 0.1 °C with a Schultheis
305 quick-reading mercury thermometer (T-4000, Miller & Weber, Inc.) or with a
306 thermocouple probe (type K) connected to a digital thermometer (Fluke 52 or Hibok
307 14). Individuals were handled manually with an insulating glove and measurements
308 recorded after 20 seconds of capture were discarded. Immediately after body
309 temperature readings, temperature at soil surface (for *Alytes*) or water surface (for *Hyla*)
310 was recorded at the exact position of the individual captured using HOBO Pendant or
311 TidBit data loggers (Onset Computer, Inc.). The measuring equipment was previously
312 calibrated against Schultheis mercury thermometers (Miller & Weber, Inc.) for the
313 range of temperatures recorded.

314

315 *Data analyses*

316 Semi-automated sound recognition procedure in three steps was used to detect calling
317 activities of all of study species throughout the time series of sound recordings: 1)
318 spectrogram cross-correlation; 2) visual spectrogram inspection; and 3) expert
319 verification. First, spectrogram cross-correlation based search (XBAT, Cornell
320 University) was used to automatically scan sound recordings and find candidate
321 vocalizations (i.e., calls initially ascribed to the study species). For this cross-
322 correlation, one set of 20–35 advertisement calls per species (sound templates) was
323 selected from ARS recordings and used to build one species-specific XBAT automated
324 signal detector (1024 FFT size; 12.5% FFT advance; 0.5–3.5 kHz frequency range; 25%
325 overlap; 10 s window size). Recorded advertisement calls from both cold and hot sites
326 were included to cover the frequency range of the advertisement calls of the study
327 species. To minimize false negatives, a low correlation threshold (0.4) was set for
328 spectrogram cross-correlation analyses. In addition to automated recognition,
329 oscillograms and spectrograms of all sound recordings were visually inspected to refine
330 the detection process (Peak 4.0, BIAS, Inc.; XBAT, Cornell University), adding new
331 findings to the list of candidate vocalizations. Finally, an expert listener verified every
332 candidate vocalization found in the previous steps, so that all false positives were
333 removed, and calling activity definitely rated with 0 (absence) or 1 (presence) in each 3-
334 min sound recording. Single advertisement calls lacking continuity from one or two
335 isolated individuals, which corresponds to tentative calling activity outside of group
336 displays, were excluded from further analyses.

337 Calling temperature was defined as the operative temperature at time of calling
338 activity in the specific calling microhabitat of each species. To determine the calling
339 temperatures for each population during the breeding season, one temperature value was

340 paired with each calling event (i.e., 3-min of sound recording with presence of calling
341 activity). Student's *t*-tests and one-way ANOVA tests were performed to compare
342 calling temperatures between populations of the same species, and between seasons of
343 the same population, respectively. Because hourly collected data suffer from
344 autocorrelation and thus they violate the basic assumption of statistical independence of
345 observations (Sokal & Rohlf, 1995), the means of calling temperatures per night were
346 calculated for each study site and used to compute the statistical analyses.
347 Autocorrelation tests of nightly calling temperature means were computed to confirm
348 the assumption of independent values (Sokal & Rohlf, 1995). Additionally, the
349 statistical parameters Student's *t*, Fisher's *F*, and *P*-value were calculated by
350 bootstrapping to prevent any lack of independence. To calculate bootstrapped
351 confidence intervals of the *t*-tests and ANOVAs, random resampling with replacement
352 of the nightly calling temperature means of for each population were computed and
353 repeated through 1000 iterations. For each test, we reported the mean of bootstrapped
354 statistic and *P*-value calculated as the following ratio: $P\text{-value} = y (n - x) / 2 n$ (Davison
355 & Hinkley, 1997), where *y* is the number of tails in the test, *n* is the number of tests
356 computed, and *x* is the number of significant *P*-values in *n* tests. Significance was set at
357 < 0.05 (i.e., above 900 significant tests for one-tailed analysis). All *t*-tests were one-
358 tailed tests because we expected calling temperature to be higher in the population
359 located at the hot thermal extreme, in the event of significant differences. Normality and
360 homoscedasticity were determined with graphical methods, and Shapiro and Levene
361 tests. Statistical analyses and figures were conducted with R v.2.10.1 (R Development
362 Core Team, 2012) and Excel PopTools 3.2.5 (Hood, 2010).

363 Besides calling temperatures, annual and potential temperatures were obtained for
364 each study site from hourly records of data loggers. Annual temperatures provide an

365 estimation of the thermal profile of each site and were determined by 8,760 records of
366 operative temperature per site, corresponding to soil temperatures in the case of *Alytes*
367 sites and to water and air temperatures in the case of *Hyla* sites (i.e., air temperatures
368 were used when standing water was not available in the breeding sites). Potential
369 temperatures provide an estimation of the set of operative temperatures recorded in each
370 site during the potential period of breeding (i.e., night-time across period with water
371 availability in breeding ponds). Therefore, potential temperatures were recorded from 1
372 h before sunset to 1 h before sunrise, while standing water occurred in the breeding site,
373 regardless of the presence or absence of calling activity, and varied from site to site.
374 Because *Alytes* spawns on land and only releases its tadpoles in water 4–5 weeks after
375 mating, the potential temperatures for these anurans were calculated taking into
376 consideration a five-week delay in relation to water availability in the breeding site. The
377 computer program Song Meter Configuration Utility 2.1 (Wildlife Acoustics, Inc.) was
378 used to obtain daily sunset and sunrise times at each study site.

379 To evaluate which environmental factors might determine calling temperatures, we
380 searched for associations between geographic differences in calling temperatures and
381 differences in three features of conspecific thermal environments (i.e., altitude, annual
382 temperature, and potential temperature). Those differences were calculated with the
383 mean value recorded throughout an entire season at the conspecific cold and hot sites
384 and were used to perform phylogenetic generalized least squares analyses (PGLS).
385 Since species may share traits of their thermal ecology as a result of a common
386 evolutionary history, observations from multiple species fail the independence
387 assumption required in statistical tests (Garland *et al.*, 1992). Thus, the PGLS approach
388 was applied to control for phylogenetic effect on the associations of the variables
389 (Freckleton *et al.*, 2002). The PGLS model also provides an estimation of the degree of

390 phylogenetic inertia in the studied associations by a phylogenetic scaling parameter (λ),
391 which ranges from 0 (i.e., minimum phylogenetic signal) to 1 (i.e., maximum
392 phylogenetic signal) under the assumption of a Brownian motion evolutionary model.
393 The estimation of lambda values and PGLS analyses were performed with the *caper*
394 package for R (R Development Core Team, 2012), using a topology with equal branch
395 lengths. The maximum likelihood value of lambda was compared against the models
396 with lambda = 0 and lambda = 1.

397 **Results**398 *Calling activity*

399 Acoustic monitoring resulted in a total of 49,550 3-min sound recordings that were
400 obtained from 2,095 days of sampling at the ten study sites (Table 2). Using the semi-
401 automated sound recognition procedure, we detected 4,926 calling events (i.e., number
402 of 3-min hourly recordings with presence of calling activity from any of the study
403 species), and paired them to one particular operative temperature of calling
404 microhabitat. By and large, the populations located at hot thermal extremes had longer
405 calling seasons and longer periods of calling activity per night than the conspecific
406 populations at cold extremes (Table 2). Number of calling nights per season ranged
407 from 24–149. Nightly duration of calling activity was highly variable even within the
408 same population (CV range, 0.34–0.70), and yielded an overall mean (\pm SD) of $6.0 \pm$
409 3.1 calling events per calling night (range, 1–16). All species showed a similar diel
410 pattern of calling activity between cold and hot populations, except *A. obstetricans*,
411 which typically began the activity at daytime in *CAo*, four hours earlier than in *HAo*.

412

413 *Thermal variation of calling microhabitats*

414 The simultaneous records of operative temperature in *CAo*, *CAC*, and *CHmo* showed
415 reduced thermal variation across the calling microhabitat of *Alytes* and *Hyla*.
416 Differences in nightly temperature means ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) among all positions of HOBO data
417 loggers averaged 0.12 ± 0.45 (range = 0.00–1.15, $n = 14$) and 0.07 ± 1.01 (range =
418 0.00–2.88, $n = 14$) for the calling microhabitat of *Alytes* in *CAo* and *CAC*, respectively,
419 and 0.05 ± 0.41 (range = 0.00–0.93, $n = 15$) for the calling microhabitat of *Hyla* in
420 *CHmo*. Nightly temperature means at each position were independent values as

421 indicated by autocorrelation analyses (for all cases, $t < 1.65$, $P > 0.12$). One-way
422 ANOVA tests showed that nightly operative temperature means measured at different
423 points of calling microhabitats were not significantly different in *CAo* ($F_{5,78} = 1.11$, $P =$
424 0.36) and in *CHmo* ($F_{3,56} = 0.93$, $P = 0.432$), but they differed in *CAC* ($F_{5,78} = 9.62$, $P <$
425 0.001). At this latter site, points across the microhabitat split into two homogeneous
426 groups according to their nightly temperature means, showing no significant differences
427 within them ($F_{2,42} = 2.27$, $p = 0.12$; $F_{2,42} = 0.55$, $P = 0.58$). The difference in the overall
428 mean temperatures between these two data sets was 1.09 °C. Therefore, we may assume
429 that operative temperatures recorded at each study site were highly representative of
430 temperatures in the calling microhabitat of the study species.

431

432 *Body temperatures and operative temperatures*

433 The cloacal readings of body temperature were highly related to temperature of the
434 calling microhabitat in all species tested, both terrestrial species, such as *A. cisternasii*
435 ($y = 1.89 + 0.76 x$, $F_{1,11} = 33.7$, $P = 0.0001$) and *A. dickhilleni* ($y = 4.36 + 0.82 x$, $F_{1,11} =$
436 221.6 , $P < 0.0001$), and aquatic species, such as *H. molleri* ($y = -7.49 + 1.46 x$, $F_{1,17} =$
437 30.4 , $P < 0.0001$) and *H. meridionalis* ($y = -0.55 + 1.10 x$, $F_{1,18} = 132.8$, $P < 0.0001$), as
438 shown by regression analysis. This linear relationship accounted for a mean (SD) of
439 $80.7\% \pm 13.8$ of variation in body temperature (coefficient of determination R^2) and
440 comparisons between body temperature and operative temperature only showed slight
441 differences that ranged in mean from -1.4 – 1.2 °C per species. These results are
442 generally concordant with what found for tropical anurans in previous studies (Navas
443 1996b, Navas *et al.*, 2013). Body temperature averaged 12.6 °C ± 1.0 (range = 10.8 –
444 14.2 °C) in *A. cisternasii*, 18.4 °C ± 3.1 (range = 13.7 – 22.0 °C) in *A. dickhilleni*, 14.8

445 °C \pm 1.8 (range = 11.6–17.9 °C) in *H. molleri*, and 18.4 °C \pm 2.5 (range = 15.2–23.4 °C)
446 in *H. meridionalis*.

447

448 *Geographic variation of calling temperatures*

449 Both *Alytes* and *Hyla* exhibited a wide geographic variation of calling temperatures,
450 with divergent thermal ranges between populations located at thermal extremes (Table
451 2; Fig. 3–5). For all study species, nightly calling temperature means measured during
452 an entire breeding season were significantly higher in the populations at hot thermal
453 extremes than in the conspecific populations at cold thermal extremes (Bootstrapped *t*-
454 tests, for *A. obstetricans*: $t_{225} = 8.68$, $P < 0.001$; for *A. cisternasii*: $t_{61} = 5.17$, $P < 0.001$;
455 for *A. dickhilleni*: $t_{64.7} = 7.30$, $P < 0.001$; for *H. molleri*: $t_{99.6} = 10.84$, $P < 0.001$; for *H.*
456 *meridionalis*: $t_{96.2} = 3.96$, $P < 0.001$). Differences in mean calling temperatures between
457 cold and hot conspecific populations ranged from 2.4–5.8 °C (Table 3), and were
458 strongly correlated with differences in mean potential temperatures between localities
459 after removing phylogenetic effects (PGLS, $F = 119.21$, $P = 0.0016$; $\lambda = 0.99$). The
460 association between calling and potential temperatures showed a slope close to 1 ($\beta \pm$
461 S.E: 0.78 ± 0.07) and explained most of the variance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.97$). Similar
462 correlations were not found between calling temperatures and annual mean
463 temperatures or altitudinal ranges of conspecific localities (PGLS, $F = 2.69$, $P = 0.20$; t
464 $= 3.75$, $P = 0.15$; respectively).

465 The overall thermal breadth of calling activity per species ranged from 15.4–20.6
466 °C, and was broader in species with greater altitudinal ranges, such as *A. obstetricans*
467 and *A. dickhilleni* (Table 2 and 3). On the whole, calling activity of *Alytes* and *Hyla*
468 mainly occurred in the warmest thermal range within potential temperatures of each

469 locality (Fig. 3 and 4), albeit all populations called at ranges of temperature exceeding
470 10 °C. Upper and lower thermal thresholds of calling were also dissimilar between
471 populations (Fig. 5), and their differences ranged from 2.1–7.3 °C for upper thresholds
472 and from 0.5–8.1 °C for lower thresholds (Table 2). Moreover, calling temperatures on
473 the first seven days after the onset of the calling season differed on average 0.2–10.1 °C
474 between conspecific localities (for *A. obstetricans*, 2.2 °C; for *A. cisternasii*, 0.2 °C; for
475 *A. dickhilleni*, 10.1 °C; for *H. molleri*, 0.8 °C; *H. meridionalis*, 3.4 °C).

476 Calling activity of all study species occurred far below (8.1–21.6 °C; Table 4) their
477 upper limits of thermal tolerance, as shown by comparison between the upper critical
478 thermal limits (CT_{max}) of the study species, previously measured in tadpoles of Iberian
479 populations (Duarte *et al.*, 2011, unpublished data; Hutchison's dynamic method;
480 thermal acclimation: 4 days at 20 °C in all species, except for *A. obstetricans*, at 10 °C),
481 and the upper thresholds of calling temperatures obtained in this study. In all study sites,
482 the upper thresholds of potential temperatures were also below CT_{max} of both *Alytes* and
483 *Hyla* (6.3–20.7 °C), except for *A. cisternasii* at its hot thermal extreme (above 1.1 °C;
484 Table 4).

485

486 *Seasonal variation of calling temperatures*

487 A three-year comparison of calling temperatures in the cold thermal extremes of *A.*
488 *cisternasii* and *H. molleri* showed that calling temperatures also may markedly differ
489 among breeding seasons (Table 5; Fig. 6 and 7). Significant differences were found in
490 nightly calling temperature means among years for both *Alytes* and *Hyla* species
491 (Bootstrapped One-way ANOVA tests, for *A. cisternasii*: $F_{2, 73} = 13.1$, $P < 0.001$; and
492 for *H. molleri*: $F_{2, 106} = 50.2$, $P < 0.001$). Although calling temperatures showed limited

493 variation between common thermal years (2007 and 2008), they experienced an acute
494 thermal increase in an extremely warm thermal year (i.e., 2009; AEMET, 2010). A rise
495 of environmental temperatures resulted in a rise of calling temperatures (Fig. 6 and 7).
496 Upper and lower thermal thresholds of calling were also dissimilar among seasons
497 (Table 5), and their differences ranged from 1.3–6.7 °C for upper thresholds and from
498 0.9–4.9 °C for lower thresholds. These differences in calling temperature were larger
499 for the aquatic species (*H. molleri*) than for the terrestrial one (*A. cisternasii*).

500 Discussion

501 A question of increasing interest is how species respond under changing thermal
502 environments. In contrast with the initial hypothesis, the patterns of geographic and
503 seasonal variation of calling temperatures revealed that study species had a wide
504 thermal breadth during sound production and exhibited calling behaviour at
505 temperatures strongly associated with the potential temperatures of each thermal
506 environment (i.e., operative temperatures during the potential period of breeding). Thus,
507 study species appeared to show a relaxed thermoregulation to such an extent that calling
508 temperatures diverged when species were exposed to distinct thermal environments.
509 Our findings support Janzen's hypothesis (1967) that predicts that the physiological
510 tolerance of organisms to temperature changes is proportional to the temperature
511 variations they experience in their habitats, so that it is expected that the thermal
512 performance breadth be broad in species, such as the study species, inhabiting temperate
513 zones with moderate annual variation of the thermal regime (Snyder & Weathers, 1975;
514 Addo-Bediako *et al.*, 2000; Ghalambor *et al.*, 2006; Sunday *et al.*, 2010). Previous
515 studies assessing the effect of temperature on calling activity have also recorded, in
516 laboratory or natural settings, acoustic displays of ectothermic taxa across temperature
517 gradients above 15 °C, suggesting that ectotherms may exhibit a wide thermal breadth
518 during calling behaviour (range of calling temperatures: above 25 °C in *Pseudacris*
519 *crucifer*, Steelman & Dorcas, 2010; 24 °C in *Hyla versicolor*, Gayou, 1984; 21 °C in
520 *Bombina bombina*, Lörcher, 1969; up to 19 °C in genus *Orchelimum*, Walker, 1975; 16
521 °C in *Hyla arborea*, Schneider, 1971). Moreover, and also in agreement with Janzen's
522 hypothesis (1967), acoustic monitoring showed that study species occurring over a
523 greater altitudinal range, and thus exposed to higher thermal variation, exhibited greater
524 thermal performance breadths.

525 This capacity to perform at a broad range of different temperatures, and the
526 consequent geographic and seasonal variation of calling temperatures, might be
527 underlain by at least two thermal adjustment mechanisms: physiological adaptation
528 (Hertz *et al.*, 1983) or plasticity of thermoregulatory behaviour by seasonal or
529 developmental acclimation (Angilletta *et al.*, 2006; Calosi *et al.*, 2008; Gvoždík, 2012).
530 On the one hand, within-species thermal preferences may be evolutionarily labile, and
531 hence susceptible to be modified by selective pressures to enhance performance levels
532 under local thermal conditions (Hertz *et al.*, 1983). Therefore, conspecific populations
533 inhabiting different thermal environments may regulate at different thermal optima due
534 to physiological adaptation. On the other hand, preferred body temperatures have been
535 shown to be plastic and dependent on previous seasonal and developmental acclimation
536 of organisms (Angilletta *et al.*, 2006; Calosi *et al.*, 2008; Gvoždík, 2012). Thus,
537 plasticity induced by local thermal conditions may increase the response capacity of
538 ectotherms to temperature changes.

539 Based on our results and on phylogenetic studies, it is likely that plasticity
540 mechanisms might be responsible for the observed patterns. First, seasonal variation of
541 calling temperatures in the same populations supports seasonal acclimation rather than
542 physiological adaptation. Second, except for *Alytes obstetricans*, there is low
543 intraspecific genetic variation between the conspecific populations studied (Martínez-
544 Solano *et al.*, 2004; Recuero *et al.*, 2007; Gonçalves *et al.*, 2009; Barth *et al.*, 2011;
545 Stöck *et al.*, 2012), and even cases of hybridization in Iberian *Hyla* (Oliveira *et al.*,
546 1991; Rosa & Oliveira, 1994; Barbadillo & Lapena, 2003), which would support
547 developmental acclimation rather than physiological adaptation. However, in the
548 absence of proper genetic and physiological controls (Garland & Adolph, 1991), it
549 remains unclear whether inter-population or interspecific differences in thermal

550 preferences are a result of phenotypic rather than genotypic adaptations (*sensu* Gould &
551 Vrba, 1982). Moreover, it has also been found that physiological divergence may occur
552 in spite of high gene flow (e.g., Leinonen *et al.*, 2013). Thus, this hypothesis should be
553 tested by individual-based experiments, instead of inter-population comparisons, to
554 verify to what extent plasticity may modulate the thermoregulatory behaviour of
555 ectotherms at time of calling activity.

556 In addition to having divergent annual calling temperatures, acoustic monitoring
557 showed that most study species also had dissimilar thermal thresholds of calling at the
558 onset of the breeding season. This suggests that other environmental or social factors
559 besides temperature contribute to trigger calling and reproductive behaviour in
560 ectotherms, as it has been shown in previous studies (Blair, 1961; Heinzmann, 1970;
561 Schneider, 1971; Blankenhorn, 1972; Salvador & Carrascal, 1990; Fukuyama &
562 Kusano, 1992; Henzi *et al.*, 1995; Brooke *et al.*, 2000; Oseen & Wassersug, 2002;
563 Murphy, 2003; Steelman & Dorcas, 2010; Llusia *et al.*, 2013a). However, our results
564 are not consistent with the proposed role of thermal thresholds as static bounds
565 determining the reproductive and calling phenology of ectothermic taxa, as suggested
566 by the link between shifts in the time of the onset of breeding season and progressive
567 rises in environmental temperatures across spatial scales (i.e., latitude and altitude
568 gradients; Schneider, 1971; Beebee, 1985; García-París *et al.*, 2004) and temporal scales
569 (i.e., recent global warming; Beebee 1995; Roy & Sparks, 2000; Gibbs & Breisch,
570 2001; Parmesan & Yohe, 2003; Hassall *et al.*, 2007; Bartomeus *et al.*, 2011). In this
571 study, we found that calling behaviour may take place at population-specific thermal
572 ranges, both at the beginning of the reproductive episodes and throughout the entire
573 season. Although, it has been well established that temperature markedly influences the
574 onset and maintenance of acoustic displays in ectotherms (e.g., Heinzmann, 1970;

575 Blankenhorn, 1972; Salvador & Carrascal, 1990; Fukuyama & Kusano, 1992; Oseen &
576 Wassersug, 2002; Steelman & Dorcas, 2010), the few studies comparing calling
577 behaviour under distinct climate regimes (e.g., Navas, 1996a; Llusia *et al.*, 2013a) have
578 also found that species may respond differently to environmental conditions, and show
579 population-specific factors, including temperature variables, that determine the temporal
580 patterns of calling activity.

581 The estimation of thermal breadth of calling behaviour in ectotherms by both *in-situ*
582 and *ex-situ* designs poses methodological and technical challenges that only recently
583 have been successfully addressed. Laboratory methods to determine the thermal
584 performance breadth of species are often unsuitable or impractical for thermal studies of
585 calling behaviour (Cowles & Bogert, 1944; Lutterschmidt & Hutchison, 1997),
586 suggesting that comparative studies under natural or semi-natural settings may afford a
587 more appropriate framework. However, such field experiments have not been conducted
588 previously, mainly because simultaneous recording of distant populations (e.g., thermal
589 extremes of species ranges) over extended periods is technically challenging and costly.
590 The recent development of *audio-trapping* techniques based on automated sound
591 recording systems (ARS; Peterson & Dorcas, 1994; Frommolt *et al.*, 2008; Obrist *et al.*,
592 2010) now allows for long-term acoustic monitoring of multiple populations (Bridges &
593 Dorcas, 2000; Oseen & Wassersug, 2002; Steelman & Dorcas, 2010; Llusia *et al.*,
594 2013a). Furthermore, the use of these new techniques provides enhanced detection,
595 absence of disturbance, and reduced observer bias (Shirose *et al.*, 1997; Acevedo &
596 Villanueva-Rivera, 2006; Llusia *et al.*, 2011). Yet before the *audio-trapping*
597 techniques can become more widespread, new and more sophisticated automated
598 species-recognition software needs to be developed.

599 Our findings imply that global temperature rises would not directly jeopardise
600 calling behaviour in the study species, as suggested by their wide thermal breadth and
601 by increases of calling temperatures in extremely warm populations and seasons. The
602 compensatory potential of shifts in thermal preferences by plasticity mechanisms may
603 provide species with means of coping with climate change (Calosi *et al.*, 2008;
604 Gvoždík, 2012). Moreover, the comparison between the upper critical thermal limits
605 (CT_{max}) of the study species with the upper thresholds of calling and potential
606 temperatures obtained in this study, indicates that calling microhabitats supply operative
607 temperatures during the potential period of breeding that were also markedly below
608 CT_{max} throughout the breeding season. *Alytes* and *Hyla* could therefore behaviourally
609 thermoregulate within the range of their thermal tolerances, and keep calling activity far
610 below their CT_{max} in all study sites. As shown in previous studies, ectotherms in
611 temperate zones might be less constrained by regional temperature increases relative to
612 lower-altitude ectotherms (Deutsch *et al.*, 2008; Tewksbury *et al.*, 2008; Huey *et al.*,
613 2009; Duarte *et al.*, 2011). However, it should be noted that predictions based on critical
614 thermal limits are probably little conservative, and may underestimate the exposure risk
615 of species to stressful thermal environments. It might be expected that adults performing
616 highly energy-demanding physiological or behavioural functions, such as calling
617 activity, be constrained by narrower thermal bounds than those determined in larvae by
618 the sub-lethal endpoints (i.e., CT_{max} and CT_{min} ; Lutterschmidt & Hutchison, 1997).

619 Climate change scenarios for the Mediterranean Basin suggest that this might be
620 one of the most climatically altered regions in the coming decades (Solomon *et al.*,
621 2007; Giorgi & Lionello, 2008), with future rises of annual maximum temperatures
622 above 4 °C for the Iberian Peninsula, but also decreases of annual run-off water volume
623 between 23 and 30%, mainly in spring and summer (Alcamo *et al.*, 2007; Trigo &

624 Palutikof, 2001; Paredes *et al.*, 2006; Solomon *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, besides shifts in
625 thermal environments, climate-change-induced reduction of the availability of water
626 will presumably have a significant impact on temperate amphibians, as has been
627 predicted by assessing their realized ecological niches (Araújo *et al.*, 2006). On the
628 other hand, differences in thermal dynamics of the specific calling and reproductive
629 microhabitats (Navas, 1996b, Navas *et al.*, 2013; Llusia *et al.*, 2013b) may promote
630 differences in the vulnerability to climate change in ectotherms. Our results showed that
631 aquatic species (*Hyla*) experienced larger seasonal increases in calling temperatures
632 than terrestrial ones (*Alytes*) in extremely warm breeding seasons. Thus, specific
633 reproductive strategies and microhabitat selection influenced exposure to changing
634 temperatures (e.g., do Amaral *et al.*, 2002). However, these findings contrast with those
635 found for tropical anurans (Navas, 1996b), for which environmental temperatures were
636 less variable in aquatic species than in terrestrial ones. Given that, besides sound
637 production, other features of acoustic communication in ectotherms are also strongly
638 temperature-dependent (e.g., *sound propagation*, Van Staaden & Römer, 1997; Penna *et*
639 *al.*, 2006; *sound reception*, Moffat & Capranica 1976; Stiebler & Narins, 1990; Fay &
640 Popper, 1999; Narins 2000; and *post-reception behaviour*, Walker, 1957; Gerhardt,
641 1978; Gerhardt & Murphy, 1980; Pires & Hoy 1992; Gray & Cade, 2000), the
642 understanding of how ectotherms deal with heterogeneous and changing thermal
643 environments related to their specific reproductive habits and simultaneously with their
644 physiological and ecological constraints to establish effective acoustic communication
645 will be a challenging aim for future studies.

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663

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Table 1. Thermal conditions in the study sites of calling activity of *Alytes* and *Hyla*, located at their Iberian thermal extremes. *Level of thermal extremity* represents the percentage of UTM 10x10 km squares in the Iberian distribution of species (1,970 UTM squares for *A. obstetricans*, 983 for *A. cisternasii*, 133 for *A. dickhilleni*, 1,257 for *H. molleri*, and 1,074 for *H. meridionalis*; Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system; Pleguezuelos *et al.*, 2002; Loureiro *et al.*, 2008) with an annual mean temperature below (in the case of hot extremes) or above (in the case of cold extremes) the annual mean temperature of the study site (see Fig. 2; Hijmans *et al.*, 2005).

No.	Locality	Species	Thermal extreme	Label	Latitude (N), Longitude (W)	Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	Annual Mean Temp. (°C)	Level of thermal extremity (%)	Monitoring year
1	Lago Cerveriz	<i>A. obstetricans</i>	Cold	CAo	43°03', 6°06'	1666	7.61	94.72	2009
2	Coimbra	<i>A. obstetricans</i>	Hot	HAo	40°12', 8°24'	96	15.95	95.84	2009
3	Fresnedillas de la Oliva	<i>A. cisternasii</i>	Cold	CAC	40°29', 4°08'	817	12.44	88.51	2007-2009
4	Almadén de la Plata	<i>A. cisternasii</i>	Hot	HAc	37°47', 6°04'	443	17.10	94.81	2007
5	Baza	<i>A. dickhilleni</i>	Cold	CAd	37°22', 2°51'	2025	9.99	95.49	2007
6	Los Guájares	<i>A. dickhilleni</i>	Hot	HAd	36°52', 3°37'	700	15.95	97.74	2007
7	Valle de Lago	<i>H. molleri</i>	Cold	CHmo	43°02', 6°08'	1490	7.61	98.57	2007-2009
8	Castelo de Vide	<i>H. molleri</i>	Hot	HHmo	39°22', 7°28'	408	15.40	77.57	2007
9	Castelo de Vide	<i>H. meridionalis</i>	Cold	CHme	39°22', 7°28'	408	15.40	73.09	2007
10	Doñana	<i>H. meridionalis</i>	Hot	HHme	36°59', 6°26'	3	17.88	96.93	2007

Table 2. Geographic variation of calling temperatures (°C) and calling activity of *Alytes* and *Hyla* at their Iberian thermal extremes. Calling events are records of calling activity within 3-min of sound recordings hourly obtained by *audio-trapping* techniques over an entire breeding season.

Species	Thermal extreme	Label	Calling temperature (°C)		Calling events	Calling events per night			Calling season	No. of days monitored
			mean ± SD	range		mean ± SD	range	N		
<i>Alytes obstetricans</i>	Cold	CAo	13.8 ± 3.5	3.3–23.9	649	8.3 ± 3.8	1–16	78	May - Aug	145
	Hot	HAo	17.6 ± 2.2	10.5–21.5	943	6.3 ± 3.4	1–14	149	Feb - Sep	224
<i>Alytes cisternasii</i>	Cold	CAC	18.2 ± 2.2	12.7–23.2	167	7.0 ± 4.9	1–14	24	Aug - Nov	337
	Hot	HAC	20.5 ± 3.2	13.2–30.1	355	9.1 ± 4.4	1–15	39	Aug - Nov	97
<i>Alytes dickhilleni</i>	Cold	CAd	10.3 ± 4.1	2.0–19.3	212	3.7 ± 2.6	1–11	68	Apr - Aug	197
	Hot	HAd	16.2 ± 2.8	10.1–21.9	127	4.3 ± 2.1	1–8	30	Mar - Oct	273
<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold	CHmo	13.3 ± 2.4	7.8–18.4	138	3.6 ± 2.1	1–9	38	Apr - Jun	349
	Hot	HHmo	18.9 ± 3.6	10.7–25.4	472	5.6 ± 1.9	1–10	84	Jan - Jul	160
<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>	Cold	CHme	16.9 ± 3.2	11.0–24.2	289	5.0 ± 2.5	1–10	58	Jan - Jun	141
	Hot	HHme	19.5 ± 2.1	14.5–26.4	855	7.2 ± 3.2	1–13	117	Dec - May	172

Table 3. Geographic variation in altitude and thermal parameters (annual, potential and calling temperatures) of the study sites. Potential temperature corresponds to operative temperature (one per hour; °C) in a specific calling microhabitat during the potential period of breeding. Potential temperature was recorded at night (i.e., from 1 h before sunset to 1 h before sunrise), while standing water was available in the breeding site, regardless of the presence or absence of calling activity. For the genus *Alytes*, potential temperatures were calculated taking into consideration a five-week delay in relation to water availability because of its terrestrial mating habits.

Species	Thermal extreme	Label	Potential temperature (°C)			Altitude range (m.a.s.l.)	Geographic variation		
			mean ± SD	range	N		Mean calling temp. (°C)	Mean potential temp. (°C)	Annual mean temp. (°C)
<i>Alytes obstetricans</i>	Cold	CAo	9.8 ± 5.9	0.1–28.6	3588	1570	3.8	4.1	8.3
	Hot	HAo	13.9 ± 3.9	3.6–21.5	5027				
<i>Alytes cisternasii</i>	Cold	CAC	10.9 ± 5.2	0.3–24.5	4357	374	2.4	3.4	4.7
	Hot	HAc	14.3 ± 7.0	1.4–39.3	4329				
<i>Alytes dickhilleni</i>	Cold	CAd	8.2 ± 5.4	0.0–20.1	3837	1325	5.8	7.1	6.0
	Hot	HAd	15.3 ± 5.7	2.5–31.3	5721				
<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold	CHmo	7.7 ± 3.9	1.2–19.3	3284	1082	5.6	7.4	7.8
	Hot	HHmo	15.1 ± 5.5	6.1–29.3	4087				
<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>	Cold	CHme	15.1 ± 5.5	6.1–29.3	4087	405	2.5	3.4	2.5
	Hot	HHme	18.5 ± 3.2	11.5–29.1	2620				

Table 4. Comparison between the upper thresholds of calling and potential temperatures (°C) and the upper critical thermal limits (CT_{max}) of the study species (Duarte *et al.*, 2011, unpublished data). CT_{max} measurements were obtained in tadpoles of Iberian populations, using Hutchison's dynamic method and with a previous thermal acclimation of 4 days at 20 °C in all species, except for *A. obstetricans*, for which thermal acclimation was at 10 °C. For description of potential temperature see Table 3.

Species	Thermal extreme	Label	CT_{max} (°C)	CT_{max} - Max calling temp. (°C)	CT_{max} - Max potential temp. (°C)
<i>Alytes obstetricans</i>	Cold	CAo	38.0	14.1	9.4
	Hot	HAo		16.5	16.5
<i>Alytes cisternasii</i>	Cold	CAc	38.2	15.0	13.7
	Hot	HAc		8.1	-1.1
<i>Alytes dickhilleni</i>	Cold	CAd	37.6	18.3	17.5
	Hot	HAd		15.7	6.3
<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold	CHmo	40.0	21.6	20.7
	Hot	HHmo		14.6	10.7
<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>	Cold	CHme	39.8	15.6	10.5
	Hot	HHme		13.4	10.7

Table 5. Seasonal variation of calling temperatures (°C) and calling activity of *Alytes cisternasii* and *Hyla molleri* at their cold thermal extremes. Calling events are records of calling activity within 3-min of sound recordings hourly obtained by *audio-trapping* techniques over an entire breeding season.

Species	Thermal extreme	Label	Year	Calling temperature (°C)		Calling events	Calling events per night		
				mean ± SD	range		mean ± SD	range	N
<i>Alytes cisternasii</i>	Cold	CAc	2007	18.2 ± 2.2	12.7–23.2	167	7.0 ± 4.9	1–14	24
			2008	18.7 ± 3.9	11.8–25.2	188	6.3 ± 4.5	1–16	16
			2009	19.9 ± 6.2	13.6–28.6	124	5.6 ± 3.5	1–12	12
<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold	CHmo	2007	13.3 ± 2.4	7.8–18.4	138	3.6 ± 2.1	1–9	38
			2008	13.9 ± 2.9	9.2–19.7	177	3.9 ± 2.4	1–9	45
			2009	18.6 ± 4.7	12.7–25.1	119	4.6 ± 2.7	1–8	26

Fig. 1 Location of study sites (white circles) and geographic distribution of the genus *Alytes* (a) and *Hyla* (b) in the Iberian Peninsula (Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system; Pleguezuelos *et al.*, 2002; Loureiro *et al.*, 2008). Species ranges are plotted through 10x10 km UTM squares with presence of *Alytes obstetricans* (grey points), *A. cisternasii* (open squares), *A. dickhilleni* (black points), *Hyla molleri* (open squares), and *H. meridionalis* (grey points). 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9: *CAo*, *CAC*, *CAd*, *CHmo* and *CHme*, respectively, i.e., populations at the cold Iberian thermal extreme of the study species. 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10: *HAo*, *HAc*, *HAd*, *HHmo* and *HHme*, respectively, i.e., populations at the hot Iberian thermal extreme of the study species.

Fig. 2 Frequency distribution of annual mean temperature (°C) in 10x10 km UTM squares of the Iberian range of the study species (Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system; Hijmans *et al.*, 2005). Arrows show annual mean temperature in UTM squares of each study site, which determines their *level of thermal extremity* (see Table 1). *CAo*, *CAC*, *CAd*, *CHmo* and *CHme*: populations at the cold Iberian thermal extreme of the study species. *HAo*, *HAc*, *HAd*, *HHmo* and *HHme*: populations at the hot Iberian thermal extreme of the study species.

Fig. 3 Comparison of calling temperatures (grey areas), potential temperatures (white areas), and annual temperatures (dashed areas) between localities at the cold (left side) and hot (right side) Iberian thermal extremes of the genus *Alytes* (terrestrial species). Boxplots consist of median (dark horizontal line), 1st-3rd quartile range (box) and range (whiskers) of these variables. Vertical plots represent frequency distributions of data (histograms). For each locality, values correspond to operative temperatures (one per hour; °C) in the calling microhabitat of *Alytes* during calling activity and over one entire breeding season (calling temperature), at night and while standing water was available in the breeding site, regardless of the presence or absence of calling activity (potential temperature), and during the whole year (annual temperature). Potential temperatures were calculated taking into consideration a five-week delay in relation to water availability because of its terrestrial mating habits.

Fig. 4 Comparison of calling temperatures (grey areas), potential temperatures (white areas), and annual temperatures (dashed areas) between localities at the cold (left side) and hot (right side) Iberian thermal extremes of the genus *Hyla* (aquatic species). Boxplots consist of median (dark horizontal line), 1st-3rd

quartile range (box) and range (whiskers) of these variables. Vertical plots represent frequency distributions of data (histograms). For each locality, values correspond to operative temperatures (one per hour; °C) in the calling microhabitat of *Hyla* during calling activity and over one entire breeding season (calling temperature), at night and while standing water was available in the breeding site, regardless of the presence or absence of calling activity (potential temperature), and during the whole year (annual temperature). Since most of the breeding points were temporary water bodies, annual temperature correspond to air temperature recorded 15–35 cm above ground that surround breeding points.

Fig. 5 Calling temperatures of populations at the cold (white boxes) and hot (grey boxes) Iberian thermal extremes of the study species. Boxplots consist of median (dark horizontal line), 1st-3rd quartile range (box) and range (whiskers) of calling temperature. For each locality, values correspond to operative temperatures (one per hour; °C) in the calling microhabitat of *Alytes* (terrestrial species) and *Hyla* (aquatic species) during calling activity and over one entire breeding season.

Fig. 6 Frequency distributions of calling temperatures (°C) in the cold Iberian thermal extremes of *Alytes cisternasii* (CAc) and *Hyla molleri* (CHmo) across three breeding seasons: 2007 (black triangles), 2008 (white triangles) and 2009 (circles). Values correspond to nightly temperature means.

Fig. 7 Seasonal variation of calling temperatures (°C) in the cold Iberian thermal extremes of *Alytes cisternasii* (CAc) and *Hyla molleri* (CHmo) across three breeding seasons (2007, 2008 and 2009). Boxplots consist of median (dark horizontal line), 1st-3rd quartile range (box) and range (whiskers) of these variables. Values correspond to nightly temperature means.

(a)

(b)

(a) *Alytes obstetricans*

(b) *Alytes cisternasii*

(c) *Alytes dickhilleni*

(b) *Hyla meridionalis*

Proportion of records per temperature interval

